

Imagining the future of biocultural diversity conservation

ABRUCENA

Almería. Natural and National Park of Sierra Nevada

Inhabitants: 1.208

A mountainous municipality traditionally dedicated to agriculture. This is done on terraces and irrigated through channels (since the Arab era). Small agricultural plots (family-owned) with gardens, fruit trees, and olive trees.

In many rural areas, culture and biodiversity are intertwined and rely on each other. In these places, traditional agriculture and its products have deep connections with the culture of the community, encompassing folk festivals, typical dishes, songs, and traditional knowledge of the region.

Past and present: biocultural element that are conserved currently

Local population from Abrucena (both women and men) widely perceive and recognize the biocultural diversity provided by the rural environment, identifying multiple examples: traditional practices, knowledge, and wisdom, as well as cultural traditions.

Preserve and recover

When they envisioned the ideal future, they recognized 89 elements of biocultural diversity that they would like to have in that future. The results highlight the desire to recover biocultural diversity while associating it with positive emotions.

1/ Removing the leaves from the corn. 2/ Traditional recipe. 3/ Traditional recipe. 4/ Plant. 5/ Tradition. 6/ Tradition. 7/ traditional irrigation channel. 8/ Food processing and preparation of dry pork. 9/ Festivity and preparation of the bullring. 10/The town crier. 11/ Enjoying the outdoor air with neighbors. 12/ Traditional recipe. 13/ Traditional irrigation channels. 14/ "Migas": Breadcrumbs, traditional recipe.

How to achieve the desired future to protect biocultural diversity?

The main strategies proposed by the local population were: improving agriculture and crop irrigation, passing on traditional knowledge and practices, and promoting nature tourism in the area.

STRATEGIES PROPOSED BY WOMEN:

- Workshops for knowledge transmission, such as handling esparto or gathering traditional plants.
- Intergenerational workshops.
- Create cooperatives to enhance the value of local agricultural products.
- Maintenance of traditional irrigation channels (acequias) and 'careos'.
- Allow greater uses in the Sierra (Sierra Nevada Natural Park).
- Provide professional training in local highschools to create specific training programs.
- Promote population attraction by offering village living incentives such as telecommuting and improved road connectivity.

Women identified a greater number of strategies than men

17 **10**

STRATEGIES PROPOSED BY MEN:

- Reduce land concentration and diversify crops.
- Implement a tourism plan.
- Promote communal work.
- Revive pasturing (transhumance).
- Encourage entrepreneurship and new businesses in the village.

24 STRATEGIES AIMED AT CONSERVATION AND RECOVERY

